

Defect-engineered Ga-K-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene@TiO_{2-x} ternary heterojunction via spontaneous MXene oxidation for enhanced photocatalytic hydrogen evolution

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ABSTRACT

The development of ternary heterojunction photocatalysts that simultaneously address sluggish charge separation kinetics, narrow spectral response, and interfacial instability remains a formidable bottleneck for efficient solar-driven hydrogen evolution. Herein, we report a defect-engineered Ga/K co-doped polymeric carbon nitride (Ga-K-PCN) coupled with Ti₃C₂ MXene-derived TiO_{2-x} via spontaneous oxidation, constructing a ternary heterojunction for superior photocatalytic hydrogen production. The Ti₃C₂ MXene serves as both a structural template and a reducing agent, enabling the in situ formation of oxygen-deficient TiO_{2-x} through controlled oxidation while maintaining interfacial Ti-O-C bonding with the Ga-K-PCN matrix. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations and spectroscopic analyses reveal that Ga/K co-doping induces mid-gap states in PCN, broadening visible-light absorption, while TiO_{2-x} acts as electron trap to suppress carrier recombination. The synergistic interplay between the ternary components establishes a unique charge transfer mechanism, accelerating carrier separation and enhancing redox potentials. The optimized photocatalyst achieves a remarkable hydrogen evolution rate of 925 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹ under visible light, 7.1-fold higher than pristine PCN, with an apparent quantum efficiency of 1.085% at 420 nm. Furthermore, the heterojunction exhibits excellent stability over 480 min of cycling, attributed to the robust interfacial coupling and defect-mediated self-healing properties. This work provides a novel strategy for leveraging MXene oxidation dynamics and defect engineering to construct high-performance ternary photocatalysts for sustainable energy applications.

1. Introduction

The rational design of multifunctional heterostructures by integrating two-dimensional (2D) materials with complementary properties has emerged as a promising strategy for advancing applications in photocatalysis [1], energy storage [2], and electronic devices [3,4]. Among these materials, Ti₃C₂ MXene, a member of the rapidly growing MXene family, has attracted significant attention due to its exceptional electrical conductivity, tunable surface chemistry, and high mechanical stability [5,6,7]. However, a critical challenge hindering its practical utilization lies in its inherent susceptibility to oxidation under ambient conditions, which leads to the irreversible degradation of its metallic

properties [7,8]. Conventionally viewed as a degradation pathway, this oxidation process predominantly yields stoichiometric TiO₂ with limited electronic tunability [9]. However, recent advances suggest that non-stoichiometric titanium oxides (e.g., TiO_{2-x} containing mixed Ti³⁺/Ti⁴⁺ states and oxygen vacancies) could exhibit superior charge transport properties compared to their fully oxidized counterparts [10, 11], owing to the formation of defect-mediated electronic states within the bandgap [12]. Intriguingly, the spontaneous oxidation of MXenes under controlled conditions may provide a unique route to synthesize such oxygen-deficient TiO_{2-x}, while preserving partial MXene conductivity [13], a hypothesis that remains largely unexplored in composite material design.

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Meanwhile, polymeric carbon nitride (PCN)-based materials, particularly those modified with metal dopants [14,15], have shown remarkable potential in catalysis owing to their tailored band structures and abundant active sites [16,17,18]. Sun et al. investigated the role of Ni-Fe dual atomic sites in atomically dispersed metal-doped PCN for the oxygen evolution reaction OER [19]. The results demonstrated that the Ni-Fe dual sites synergistically optimized the electronic structure and reaction activity, significantly enhancing the catalytic performance and stability of OER. Wu et al. achieved a notable improvement in the photocatalytic degradation of methylamine by incorporating alkali metal dopants and enriching cyano groups in crystalline $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ [20]. This approach modified the band structure and facilitated charge carrier separation, leading to enhanced photocatalytic efficiency. Furthermore, the integration of MXene with PCN has been widely reported as well, particularly for energy conversion and catalytic applications. For instance, Maadh et al. introduced bandgap-engineered MXene- C_3N_4 interfacial layer in perovskite solar cells [21], which reduced recombination losses and significantly enhanced charge carrier separation and transport efficiency, thereby improving the overall photo-conversion performance of the solar cell. Yang et al. constructed a protonated $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4/\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2$ MXene Schottky heterojunction via an in situ synthesis method [22], which significantly improved the catalyst's light absorption capability and enhanced the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution efficiency. However, existing studies have predominantly focused on the synergistic effects of the combined materials [23,24], while the property changes within the composite induced by the self-oxidation of MXene have been deliberately overlooked [25,26]. This phenomenon raises an intriguing question: Could the unintentional TiO_2 formation, typically deemed undesirable, instead serve as a structural "bridge" to synergistically couple the advantages of metal doped PCN and MXene [26,27]?

Building upon the previously reported Ga-K-PCN single-atom photocatalyst from Ohno et al. (a gallium/potassium co-modified polymeric carbon nitride with enhanced visible-light absorption and charge separation) [28], we initially sought to construct a Ga-K-PCN/ Ti_3C_2 heterojunction to synergize the photocatalytic merits of both components. Unexpectedly, during the composite fabrication under ambient conditions, the Ti_3C_2 MXene underwent partial oxidation to form a TiO_{2-x} phase with coexisting $\text{Ti}^{3+}/\text{Ti}^{4+}$ species, rather than fully oxidized TiO_2 . This serendipitous discovery led to a ternary architecture: Ga-K-PCN anchored on a $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2/\text{TiO}_{2-x}$ hybrid substrate, as depicted in Fig. 1. The resulting oxygen vacancies in TiO_{2-x} , as evidenced by electron paramagnetic resonance spectroscopy, create mid-gap states that not

only enhance visible-light harvesting but also serve as electron reservoirs to suppress carrier recombination, a feature unattainable in conventional TiO_2 -based composites. This study redefines the role of MXene oxidation from a material failure mechanism to a precision tool for designing high-performance composites. By leveraging the self-limiting oxidation behavior of Ti_3C_2 , we achieve simultaneous optimization of light absorption, charge dynamics, and environmental stability, a triad of challenges that have persistently plagued conventional photocatalyst design. Our findings not only provide a paradigm shift in MXene-derived material engineering but also open new avenues for developing defect-mediated smart composites with broad applications in solar energy conversion and beyond.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and reagents

All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received without further purification. The water used in all experiments was purified through a Millipore system.

2.2. Synthesis of Ga-K-PCN

A bimetallic co-doping synthesis approach was employed. Briefly, gallium(III) nitrate hexahydrate and potassium chloride powder were precisely weighed at Ga/K molar ratios of 10:1, 10:3, and 10:5, then dissolved in a mixed solution of 100 mL ethanol and 20 mL deionized water. Ultrasonication was applied for 120 min to facilitate dissolution. Subsequently, the solution was combined with 4 g of melamine powder and continuously stirred to ensure homogeneous dispersion. The mixture was then concentrated using a rotary evaporator, and the resulting white powder was transferred to a tubular furnace under a nitrogen atmosphere. The material was calcined at 560 °C for 4 hours, yielding a brownish-yellow powder, denoted as Ga-K-PCN.

2.3. Synthesis of few-layer Ti_3C_2 MXene

1 g of Ti_3AlC_2 MAX powder was stirred in a mixed solution of lithium fluoride and concentrated hydrochloric acid at 55 °C in an oil bath for 7 days. The etched precipitate was collected via centrifugation and repeatedly washed with deionized water until the pH approached 6. The material was then dispersed in 30 mL of deionized water via

Fig. 1. Illustration of the fabrication procedure for Ga-K-PCN/ Ti_3C_2 @ TiO_{2-x} heterojunctions.

ultrasonication for 30 minutes to form a uniform suspension. Subsequently, 25 wt% tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAOH) was added to the dispersion, followed by continuous stirring at room temperature for 12 hours. The resulting mixture underwent three cycles of centrifugation and rinsing. The collected supernatant was freeze-dried. The obtained black powder was identified as a few-layer Ti_3C_2 MXene.

2.4. Synthesis of Ga-PCN/ Ti_3C_2 @ TiO_2 -X heterojunction

A series of heterojunction composites were synthesized using a one-pot hydrothermal method. First, 100 mg of Ga-K-PCN powder and a specific amount of Ti_3C_2 solid were dispersed in 30 mL of deionized water. The solution was uniformly mixed by magnetic stirring in a dark environment. The resulting solution was then transferred to a 100 mL three-necked flask and reacted under a 90 °C water bath for 2 hours. After the reaction, the solution was allowed to cool naturally to room temperature, followed by vacuum filtration to obtain the solid product. The product was washed alternately with deionized water and ethanol three times, then collected and dried in a 60 °C oven for more than 12 hours. The dried product was ground using a mortar and pestle to obtain the Ga-K-PCN/ Ti_3C_2 @ TiO_2 -X-A powder, labeled as GTT-A (where A is set to 3%, 5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%, respectively, representing the mass percentage of Ti_3C_2 in the mixture). A detailed list of the compositions and naming conventions for the experimental catalysts is provided in Table S1.

2.5. Characterization of materials

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the synthesized samples were obtained using a D8 ADVANCE diffractometer with a Cu K α radiation source, covering a scanning range of $2\theta = 10^\circ$ - 80° at a scanning speed of 5° min^{-1} . Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were recorded using a Nicolet Nexus 470 spectrometer in the range of 400-4000 cm^{-1} , with KBr as the substrate. The morphology and elemental distribution of the samples were analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-7800F) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM, FEI Talos 200S). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was conducted using a Thermo Scientific K-Alpha spectrometer. The pore size distribution (PSD) and specific surface area (S_{BET}) of the samples were measured using a BETA202A surface area and pore size analyzer, with a degassing temperature of 300 °C for 3 hours. Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) diffuse reflectance spectroscopy was recorded using a UV 2600 spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 200-1400 nm, with high-purity BaSO_4 as the reference material. The steady-state photoluminescence (PL) spectra were obtained using a QuantaMasterTM-40 fluorescence spectrophotometer with an excitation wavelength of 365 nm. Photoelectrochemical (PEC) measurements, including electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), Mott-Schottky (MT) analysis, and photocurrent response, were performed using a CHI 660E electrochemical workstation in a three-electrode system: a platinum sheet as the counter electrode, an Ag/AgCl electrode as the reference electrode, and the semiconductor sample loaded onto an FTO electrode as the working electrode. The working electrode was prepared as follows: a defined amount of ethyl cellulose and the sample (mass ratio of 1:10) were dispersed in 3 mL ethanol, subjected to ultrasonication for 30 minutes, and thoroughly ground. The resulting dispersion was uniformly applied onto a $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ FTO conductive glass substrate and dried at 100 °C for 1 hour to obtain the corresponding working electrode. The photocurrent response measurements were conducted in 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 solution, while the EIS and MT tests were performed in 0.01 M $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6/\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (1:1) solution.

2.6. Density functional theory calculations (DFT)

All calculations were based on density functional theory (DFT) with geometry optimization using the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE)

functional within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) [29, 30]. A vacuum layer of 20 Å was applied in the direction perpendicular to the surface to avoid interlayer interactions. Additionally, a cutoff energy of 520 eV and Monkhorst's K-point sampling were used. A $23 \times 23 \times 1$ grid was employed for the PBE functional calculations in the 2D Brillouin zone, while a $17 \times 17 \times 1$ grid was used for the HSE06 functional. All structures were fully relaxed until the convergence criteria for forces and energy reached 0.01 eV/Å and 10^{-5} eV, respectively. To obtain more accurate electronic and optical properties, the HSE06 functional was utilized [31]. Furthermore, the DFT-D3 method with Grimme corrections was applied to describe weak van der Waals interactions between layers [32], and dipole moment corrections were also considered throughout the calculations.

2.7. Photocatalytic water splitting for hydrogen production

10 mg of the catalyst was dispersed in 40 mL of an aqueous solution containing 10% (v/v) triethanolamine as a hole scavenger, and then ultrasonicated for 30 min to form a uniform suspension. The mixture was then transferred into a quartz reactor, with all openings sealed using sealing films. Nitrogen gas was purged through the system for 15 minutes while maintaining continuous stirring to remove residual air. A 300 W xenon lamp equipped with a cutoff filter ($\lambda > 420 \text{ nm}$) was used as the light source, positioned at 10 cm from the reactor and the light intensity was calibrated to 100 $\text{mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$. The generated hydrogen was analyzed using a GC-7806 gas chromatograph equipped with a 5Å molecular sieve column and nitrogen as the carrier gas. A standard calibration curve correlating hydrogen volume with peak area was established using an external standard method, and the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution yield (μmol) was determined based on the peak area of the GC output.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Morphology and surface observation

The morphological characteristics and structural features of the samples were initially analyzed using field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM). As shown in Fig. 2a-b, both PCN-based samples exhibited randomly stacked sheet-like structures (Fig. 2a-b). However, compared to the dense and smooth layers of pristine PCN, $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-K}_3$ -PCN presented a more pronounced porous structure. This structural change is likely attributed to the introduction of the metal precursor, which may have altered the thermal polymerization process during heat treatment [28,33]. Ti_3C_2 MXene exhibited distinct jagged edges and unfolded nanosheet characteristics (Fig. 2c), confirming the successful acid etching and exfoliation process. The GTT heterojunction was composed of irregularly curved nanosheets (Fig. 2d). However, the interfacial contact between the different components in the heterojunction could not be clearly observed in the SEM images. Therefore, representative samples $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-K}_3$ -PCN and GTT-10% were chosen for an in-depth analysis using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) and selected area electron diffraction (SAED). As shown in Fig. 2e, the distinct contrast in color intensity confirms the tight integration of the nanosheets. Detailed examination of the GTT-10% sample (Fig. 2f-g) reveals distinct lattice fringes with spacings of 0.27 nm and 0.25 nm, corresponding to the (103) plane of Ti_3C_2 (JCPDS #52-0875) [34] and the (101) plane of TiO_2 (JCPDS #09-0240) [35], respectively. This unexpected result suggests the occurrence of localized self-oxidation of Ti_3C_2 within the heterojunction. Additionally, the SAED patterns shown in Fig. 2h, featuring diffraction rings of varying diameters, further validate these observations. In contrast, no lattice fringes were observed in the HRTEM images of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-K}_3$ -PCN (Fig. S1a-cFig. S1a-c), and its SAED pattern similarly exhibited no crystalline features (Fig. S1d). This indicates that both gallium and potassium are doped in atomic form within the interlayer structure of the tri-s-triazine units in carbon

Fig. 2. SEM image of (a) PCN, (b) Ga₁₀-k₃-PCN, (c) Ti₃C₂ MXene and (d) Ga₁₀-K₃-PCN/Ti₃C₂@TiO_{2-x}-10% (GTT-10%), (e) TEM image, (f-d) HRTEM, (e) SAED image and (i) Mapping images GTT-10%.

nitride, consistent with previous literature reports [28]. Elemental mapping provides a more intuitive visualization of the spatial distribution of constituent elements within the material. As displayed in

Fig. S1e, the spatial distributions of C, Ga, K, N, and O further confirm the homogeneous incorporation of metal dopants into the PCN matrix. Additionally, the presence of an extra Ti element further verifies the

Fig. 3. (a) FT-IR patterns of GTT-A% samples, (b) XRD patterns of pristine Ti₃C₂, Ga₁₀-K₃-PCN and GTT-A% samples, (c) steady state photoluminescence spectra of Ti₃C₂ and GTT-A% samples, (d) time-resolved PL spectra of PCN, Ga₁₀-PCN, Ga₁₀-K₃-PCN and GTT-10% and average fluorescence lifetime (inset).

successful synthesis of the GTT composite catalyst (Fig. 2i).

3.2. Structural characterization

FT-IR spectroscopy was employed to identify the functional groups in the photocatalyst. The spectrum of Ga-K-PCN samples exhibited distinctive fingerprint features at approximately 810 cm^{-1} and in the $1300\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, suggesting the formation of a potassium poly (heptazine imide) (K-PHI) structure [36] (Fig. S2a). Meanwhile, a vibrational peak observed at 2140 cm^{-1} indicates that the incorporation of potassium species during the synthesis process results in the formation of a metal-cyanamide complex [37] (Fig. S2a). In GTT composite, the characteristic peaks observed in the $3000\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range are ascribed to the stretching vibrations of unpolymerized amino groups (N-H and -NH_2) (Fig. 3a), likely originating from residual amino groups attached to carbon atoms (derived from melamine) [38]. Additionally, multiple absorption peaks detected in the $1200\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, correspond to the stretching vibrations of C-N and C=N bonds, reflecting the presence of aromatic ring structures in PCN (such as triazine rings or melamine structural units) [39]. Furthermore, the sharp absorption peak at 810 cm^{-1} is attributed to the out-of-plane breathing mode of the triazine or s-triazine repeating units. These observations prove that the integration of Ti_3C_2 does not disrupt the fundamental framework of PCN. However, the characteristic peaks of Ti_3C_2 MXene could not be precisely identified, prompting further XRD analysis to elucidate the crystalline phase structure and confirm the composition. All the typical peaks ascribed to Ti_3AlC_2 MAX disappeared except the (002) peak retained in the XRD pattern of Ti_3C_2 (Fig. S2b), implying the elimination of Al layers in Ti_3AlC_2 and the formation of Ti_3C_2 MXene [5]. The synthesized PCN showed two obvious peaks at 2θ values of 13.05° and 27.47° , corresponding to the (100) and (002) diffraction planes, respectively. These peaks are related to the interlayer stacking of the aromatic systems and the graphitic stacking between the layers [22] (Fig. S2c). In the Ga-K-PCN sample, the corresponding peaks were slightly shifted toward lower angles, which could be explained by the electrostatic repulsion that occurs when metal cations are incorporated into the PCN matrix. Furthermore, the intensity of these peaks gradually diminished with increasing doping levels. This phenomenon is attributed to the formation of new chemical bonds between the metal and PCN upon doping, which disrupts its crystalline structure, leading to partial amorphization and a decrease in overall structural order (Fig. S2c). Compared to pure Ti_3C_2 MXene, the (002) diffraction peak of the GTT composite shifts from 7.1° to 6.3° , implying that Ga-K-PCN intercalates between Ti_3C_2 MXene layers, resulting in increased interlayer spacing (Fig. 3b). Notably, the XRD pattern of the composite exhibits additional characteristic peaks at 21.4° , 37.4° , and 53.8° , corresponding to titanium oxide (TiO , PDF#09-0240) [40], indicating the presence of a titanium oxide phase within the composite, probably due to the intercalation of Ga-K-PCN, which exposes more active Ti atoms to oxidation. Oxide formation was unavoidable even when synthesis was performed in the dark after degassing the solvent by nitrogen stripping and was also observed in a mechanical mixture of the components prepared with a mortar and pestle. These results suggest that the oxygen-containing functional groups in Ga-K-PCN act as oxidation centers for the Ti_3C_2 surface. Detailed information will be provided in the XPS analysis section.

Photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy was used to investigate the recombination behavior of electron-hole pairs in materials. Pure PCN exhibited a strong emission peak around 450 nm , which is attributed to the energy released during the radiative recombination of free excitons near the band edge. Generally, a stronger peak indicates a faster recombination rate [41]. In contrast, the PL peak intensity of Ga-K-PCN was significantly reduced, suggesting that the recombination of photogenerated charge carriers is suppressed (Fig. S2d). This phenomenon is probably due to the metal acting as an electron or hole acceptor, capturing photogenerated electrons or holes through interfacial

interactions and thus reducing the direct recombination of charge carriers. Furthermore, the GTT samples had weaker fluorescence emission intensity than that of Ga-K-PCN, indicating that the coupling of Ti_3C_2 MXene with Ga-K-PCN further suppressed the recombination rate of radiative electron-hole pairs (Fig. 3c). This can be described as MXene providing Ga-K-PCN with a high specific surface area and continuous electronic transport channels while the inherent metallic properties of MXene enable it to act as an excellent electron transfer medium, effectively promoting charge transfer. Time-resolved transient PL was carried out to understand the dynamic migration of photogenerated charge carriers, while the fluorescence emission decay lifetime was obtained by fitting Kohlrausch-Williams-Watts function [42] (Tab. S2). It was found that $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-K}_3\text{-PCN}$ realized the shortest average decay time (τ), revealing that metal doping effectively filled the defect sites (e.g., nitrogen vacancies) in PCN and optimized the charge transport pathway network (Fig. 3d). In contrast, the GTT-10% heterojunction showed a slightly extended average decay time, indicating the longer transport pathways resulting from the large specific surface area of the composite material.

3.3. Chemical composition

High-resolution XPS spectra provided further insights into the elemental composition and corresponding chemical states of the prepared catalysts. Full region survey spectra of all photocatalysts revealed that Ti signals were detected exclusively in the GTT-10% hybrid while all elemental signals observed from $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-K}_3\text{-PCN}$ were retained (Fig. S3), confirming the successful incorporation of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-K}_3\text{-PCN}$ and Ti_3C_2 MXene. In the C 1s XPS spectrum, peaks located at approximately 288.3 eV and 284.8 eV , corresponding to $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ bonds and adventitious carbon (C-C) [43], respectively, remain visible even after metal doping (Fig. 4a). This points out that doping does not alter the chemical state of the surface carbon or disrupt the conjugated aromatic ring structure of carbon nitride. Notably, two peaks at 295.8 eV and 292.9 eV belong to the characteristic peaks of $\text{K} 2\text{p}^{3/2}$ and $\text{K} 2\text{p}^{1/2}$, respectively [28,37]. The presence of a distinct low-binding energy peak observed at approximately 281.2 eV in the GTT-10% spectrum is typically assigned to Ti-C bonds, which means the formation of strong metal-carbon interactions between carbon and titanium atoms within the Ti_3C_2 MXene structure. The N 1s spectra of $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-K}_3\text{-PCN}$ and GTT-10% can be deconvoluted into four distinct components through peak fitting analysis, which are the N-metal bond, C=N, tertiary nitrogen and -NH_x , corresponding to the binding energies at 398.3 eV , 398.9 eV , 399.9 eV and 401.2 eV for $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-K}_3\text{-PCN}$, respectively, and at 398.2 eV , 398.8 eV , 399.9 eV and 401.1 eV for GTT-10%, respectively [44] (Fig. 4b). The slight shift in binding energies of three N species also confirms the contact interaction between $\text{Ga}_{10}\text{-K}_3\text{-PCN}$ and Ti_3C_2 MXene. Previous studies have reported that potassium, owing to its relatively large ionic radius ($\sim 1.38\text{ \AA}$), preferentially occupies the interlayer voids of carbon nitride, where it coordinates with six surrounding nitrogen atoms [37,45]. The Ga 2p spectrum illustrates that the characteristic Ga-N peak appears consistently at 1118.1 eV across all samples (Fig. 4c), which indicates that the coordination between Ga and N is highly stable. To determine the oxidation state of titanium and clarify the composition of the composite, the Ti 2p orbitals were deconvoluted and analyzed comparatively. The results showed that the Ti $2\text{p}^{3/2}$ peak exhibited a reduced intensity and a shift in position compared to pure Ti_3C_2 , implying that some titanium atoms have undergone partial oxidation [44,46]. Additionally, new peaks corresponding to partially oxidized titanium bonds appear at 454.2 eV and 464.6 eV in the Ti 2p spectrum of GTT-10% (Fig. 4d). Combined with the XRD results, it can be concluded that the oxidation is not complete, and the oxide is not typical TiO_2 but rather a defective titanium oxide compound (TiO_{2-x}).

3.4. Photo-electrochemical properties

Mott-Schottky curves were tested to identify the semiconductor type

Fig. 4. High-resolution XPS spectra of pristine PCN, Ga₁₀-PCN, Ga₁₀-K₃-PCN, Ti₃C₂ MXene and GTT-10%: (a) C 1s, (b) N 1s, (c) Ga 2p and (d) Ti 2p.

and locate the band potential of the synthesized samples. The positive slopes in all the Mott-Schottky curves represent the typical characteristics of n-type semiconductors for the PCN-based catalysts (Fig S4a-e). The flat band potential measured versus the Ag/AgCl electrode were summarized in Fig. S5. For intuitive comparison, all values were further converted to potential relative to the normal hydrogen electrode (NHE) [47]:

$$E_{NHE} = E_{Ag/AgCl} + E_{Ag/AgCl}^0 \quad (1)$$

Conduction band (E_{CB}) and valence band (E_{VB}) under normal hydrogen electrode (NHE, pH=7) are calculated by [48]:

$$E_{CB} = E_{Ag/AgCl} - E_{Ag/AgCl}^0 + 0.059 \times pH \quad (2)$$

$$E_{VB} = E_{CB} + E_g \quad (3)$$

Compared to pure PCN, the incorporation of Ga and K ions into the framework results in a shift of both the conduction band and valence band to more positive potentials.

The optical absorption range and intensity of the prepared catalysts were determined using UV-Vis DRS. Pure PCN presented a typical absorption pattern centered around 420 nm, while the Ga-K-PCN samples manifested a noticeable redshift, extending their absorption into the visible light region (Fig. S6a). This improvement suggests that metal doping effectively altered the electronic band structure, leading to enhanced light-harvesting capability. Similarly, with the increasing content of Ti₃C₂ MXene, the GTT composite exhibited a further redshift in optical absorption compared to the pristine Ga-K-PCN sample, with the absorption edge extending close to 500 nm (Fig. S6b). This shift indicates that the incorporation of MXene induces a synergistic effect

between the components, enhancing the ability to utilize visible light. Additionally, a substantial increase in light absorption within the 500-800 nm range was observed. Although the enhanced absorption in this spectral region does not directly excite charge carriers in Ga-K-PCN, the photothermal effect and metallic properties of Ti₃C₂ MXene, contribute to improving local surface activity. This, in turn, enhances the overall photocatalytic efficiency and accelerates the dynamics of photo-generated charge carriers. The bandgaps of samples were estimated by the Tauc plot based on the formula [34]:

$$(\alpha h\nu)^{1/n} = B(h\nu - E_g) \quad (4)$$

where α is the absorbance, h is the Planck constant (6.62×10^{-34} J·s), and ν is the light frequency. The value of n is 2 for PCN-based samples with indirect transition semiconductor properties. The reduction in the bandgap of Ga-K-PCN may be related to the changes in the π -conjugated system caused by doping, which enhances the electron delocalization effect (Fig S6b). The incorporation of MXene established a well-structured conductive network framework (Fig 5b), which further promotes the fast separation of photogenerated electron-hole pairs.

N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms were conducted to evaluate the specific surface area and pore size distribution of photocatalysts. The N₂ adsorption-desorption curves of pure PCN, Ga₁₀K₃-PCN and GTT-10% all displayed type IV isotherms with a H₃ hysteresis loop and the N₂ adsorption reached the maximum value as the relative pressure approaches 1, indicating the presence of typical mesoporous [44] (Fig 5c). The pore size distribution curves affirmed that the majority of the pores fall within the 2-10 nm range (Fig 5d). The comparison clearly shows that GTT-10% composite have a significantly higher specific surface area and pore volume than pure PCN and Ga₁₀K₃-PCN, which is

Fig. 5. (a) UV-Vis DRS spectra and (b) bandgap of GTT-A%, (c) N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms and (d) pore size distribution of PCN, $Ga_{10}K_3$ -PCN and GTT-10%, (e) photocurrents curves and (f) EIS Nyquist plots of samples under visible light irradiation.

expected to expose more active sites for photon capture in the photocatalytic reaction.

To gain a more thorough understanding of charge transfer capability in GTT, we performed electrochemical analysis while simulating artificial sunlight conditions. The photocurrent response (I-t) curves were obtained under a 300 W xenon lamp with alternating on/off light. Generally, a stronger photocurrent intensity means a higher separation efficiency of photoexcited electrons and holes [49]. All Ga-K-PCN samples expressed high instantaneous photocurrents at the beginning and then tend to be stabilized after 50 s irradiation. The photocurrent value of $Ga_{10}K_3$ -PCN is ~ 4 times that of PCN and it also outperforms the other Ga-K-PCN samples (Fig S6c). This may be related to the formation of charge separation centers (electron traps or hole capture sites) within the carbon nitride matrix, facilitated by the electron-rich nature of potassium and the electron-deficient nature of gallium. In comparison, GTT-10% exhibited superior I-t performance and ultimately achieved the highest photocurrent value, rather than the expected GTT-20% (Fig 5e). This suggests that at an optimal blending threshold, Ti_3C_2 MXene can serve as an efficient charge transport channel for photogenerated electrons, reducing bulk resistance. However, excessive MXene loading may cover the surface-active sites, leading to competitive light absorption and consequently hindering surface redox reactions. Moreover, the movement of photogenerated electrons and holes is influenced by the intrinsic resistance of the material as well. EIS measurements from 1 Hz to 1 MHz were used to evaluate the relative impedance strength of different materials. In the high-frequency region, GTT-10% exhibited the smallest semicircle diameter, demonstrating the lowest charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}). In contrast, the semicircle radius of GTT-20% increased (Fig 5f), which can be ascribed to the excessive MXene content inducing interfacial disorder due to the electrostatic attraction (e.g., physical stacking rather than chemical bonding) (Fig. S6d), which then increases the interfacial barrier, hindering charge transfer across the interface.

3.5. Evaluation of photocatalytic H_2 generation

Initially, the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution performance (HER) of all Ga-K-PCN samples was evaluated under visible light irradiation to

identify the optimal doping ratio. Triethanolamine (TEOA) was used as the sacrificial agent. Pristine PCN showed relatively low catalytic activity ($261.34 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) due to the rapid recombination of electron-hole pairs and the poor resistance to photocorrosion. Notable, the $Ga_{10}K_3$ -PCN achieved the highest hydrogen production activity of $1028.66 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ within 120 min (Fig. 6a). However, photocatalytic activity decreased when the K^+ doping amount exceeded 3 mmol. This decline may be caused by excessive K^+ doping, which disrupted the layered structure of PCN and introduced an excessive number of defects, which ultimately acted as recombination centers for electron-hole pairs, reducing charge separation efficiency. Additionally, a high concentration of K^+ renders the material surface overly alkaline, potentially affecting the adsorption/desorption equilibrium of reaction intermediates or altering the local pH environment, thereby hindering the hydrogen evolution kinetics [50]. In the reaction system containing only Ti_3C_2 MXene, no detectable hydrogen was observed. In contrast, when Ti_3C_2 was composited with $Ga_{10}K_3$ -PCN at a weight ratio of 10 wt%, the catalyst achieved a remarkable hydrogen evolution activity of $1850 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ (Fig. 6b). Nevertheless, a further increase in the Ti_3C_2 content led to a suppression of hydrogen production, which demonstrates the "dual-edged sword effect" of MXene incorporation. At the critical and optimal ratio (approximately 10%), its positive effects, such as enhanced conductivity, interface regulation, and improved light absorption, reach their peak. However, when the threshold is exceeded, negative factors such as coverage effects, light shielding, and aggregation defects rapidly accumulate, leading to a decline in catalytic performance. The H_2 production rates for all the above-mentioned samples are summarized in Fig. S7a-b.

The experiments for the selection of sacrificial agents demonstrated that TEOA has a superior catalytic auxiliary effect compared to the other solvents (Fig. 6c), because the oxidation potential of TEOA (~ 0.2 V vs. NHE) is significantly lower than that of water oxidation (1.23 V vs. NHE) [51], allowing it to be preferentially oxidized by photo-generated holes, thus avoiding the competing water splitting pathway and improving hole consumption efficiency. Additionally, the strong electron-donating ability of the tertiary amine and hydroxyl groups allows the lone pair electrons to quickly transfer to the surface of the photocatalyst, effectively suppressing electron-hole recombination [52]. To evaluate the

Fig. 6. Photocatalytic H₂ evolution of (a) Ga-K-PCN samples and (b) GTT-A%, (c) effect of different sacrificial agent for photocatalytic H₂ evolution, (d) recycling H₂ production experiments using GTT-10%.

catalyst's stability, GTT-10% was subjected to four consecutive cycles under identical reaction conditions. During these tests the H₂ evolution activity remained unchanged (Fig. 6d), demonstrating its excellent structural stability and durability [22, 53]. Meanwhile, GTT-10% showed superior H₂ production performance compared with similar reported 2D heterojunctions or catalysts with MXene as a component (Table 1).

Subsequently, we investigated the reaction conditions to optimize the H₂ generation process. The H₂ action spectra of pristine PCN, Ga₁₀-K₃-PCN, and GTT-10% under different monochromatic light irradiation and their UV-Vis DRS data were presented simultaneously in Fig. 7a-b. Apparent quantum efficiency (AQY) is a principal factor used to evaluate the light utilization efficiency of photocatalyst, and was calculated applying different light bandpass filters with wavelengths of 370 ± 10 nm, 400 ± 10 nm and 420 ± 10 nm [28].

$$AQY(\%) = \frac{N_A \times h \times c}{I \times S \times t \times \lambda} \times \frac{[nH_2 \times 2]}{[N_A \times h \times c]} \quad (5)$$

where N_A is Avogadro's constant, h is the Planck constant, c is the speed of light, nH_2 is the amount of H₂ generated. S is the irradiated area and I is the light intensity entering the reactor, which was measured by using an optical power meter. t is the irradiation time, and λ is the wavelength of the monochromatic light. The variation in H₂ production aligned with the trend observed in the light absorption spectra of the catalysts, confirming that the catalytic reaction was unequivocally driven by light (Fig. 7a). As shown in Table S3, the AQY of GTT-10% for photocatalytic H₂ production reaches a maximum of 8.195% under 370 nm UV light but is relatively lower under 420 nm visible light (1.058%). Nevertheless, it still demonstrated advantages over pure PCN and Ga-K-PCN (Fig. 7b). This can be attributed to the fact that, although metal doping and MXene coupling extend the absorption into the visible region, the actual absorption intensity of the material at 420 nm remains

low, resulting in limited photon utilization. In contrast, 370 nm UV light possesses higher energy and is closer to the primary absorption peak, leading to a more efficient excitation process. Therefore, additional tests were conducted to evaluate the H₂ production performance of the catalyst under full-spectrum light. Notably, the H₂ production rate of GTT-10% decreased after continuous irradiation for over 1 hour across the entire wavelength range (Fig. 7c & Fig. S7c), indicating that it had approached the limit of light energy conversion. However, under visible light, the hydrogen production rate showed a linear increase.

To accurately identify the key species involved in the photocatalytic H₂ reaction, specific scavengers were added to the photocatalytic system to quench the active radicals. Fig. 7d shows that when benzoquinone (BQ, 1 mM) was introduced as a superoxide radical ($\cdot O_2^-$) scavenger into the reaction, the H₂ production efficiency significantly decreased. However, the hole (h^+) scavenger EDTA (1 mM) had a negligible impact on the final H₂ production rate, suggesting that holes do not directly participate in the reaction. In addition, adding the hydroxyl radical ($\cdot OH$) scavenger t-Butanol (TBA, 1 mM) had little effect on the H₂ generation. These results indicate that $\cdot O_2^-$ is the crucial intermediate for photocatalysis, which promotes electron utilization indirectly by regulating charge separation rather than directly participating in the hydrogen production reaction. On the other hand, scavenging h^+ helps inhibit carrier recombination as well.

3.6. DFT theoretical calculations

To further analyze the interactions between the components of the composite heterojunction, first-principles calculations based on density functional theory (DFT) were conducted. It is important to note that due to the challenges in constructing a ternary model for Ga-K-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene@TiO_{2-x} (as the TiO_{2-x} model could not be successfully established), the calculations were primarily performed using a binary model of Ga-K-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene. The Partial Density of States (PDOS)

Table 1
Comparison of photocatalytic H₂ generation performance with various photocatalysts

Photocatalyst	Reactant Solution	Light Source	H ₂ rate $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$	Ref
Ti ₃ C ₂ /g-C ₃ N ₄	10 mg samples, 50 mL aqueous solution containing 5 mL of TEOA	$\lambda > 420$ nm	727	[22]
WS ₂ /g-C ₃ N ₄	50 mg samples, 80 mL aqueous solution containing 5 mL of EtOH	$\lambda > 420$ nm	101	[54]
Zn-Ni-P/g-C ₃ N ₄	10 mg samples, 35 mL aqueous solution containing TEOA (15%)	5 W white-light	531.2	[55]
SnNb ₂ O ₆ /Ti ₃ C ₂	20 mg samples, 100 mL aqueous solution containing EtOH (20%)	$\lambda > 420$ nm	175.2	[56]
CuInS ₂ Ti ₃ C ₂ /TiO ₂	20 mg samples, 100 mL H ₂ O+15 mL Acetone +5 mL TEOA	$\lambda > 400$ nm	356.27	[57]
C-TiO ₂ /Ti ₃ C ₂ T _X	50 mg samples, 50 mL aqueous solution containing 5 mL of TEOA	$\lambda > 400$ nm	17.8	[58]
Cu-TiO ₂ @Ti ₃ C ₂ T _X	50 mg samples, 140 mL H ₂ O+15 mL methanol	$\lambda > 420$ nm	860	[59]
Ti ₃ C ₂ /g-C ₃ N ₄ /Pt	30 mg samples, 50 mL aqueous solution containing TEOA (10%)	$\lambda > 420$ nm	53	[53]
MnS/D-PCN	50 mg samples, 80 mL H ₂ O+20 mL methanol	$\lambda > 420$ nm	670.5	[60]
NiS/PCN	50 mg samples, 65 mL H ₂ O+6.5 mL TEOA	$\lambda > 420$ nm	142.9	[61]
FeTPPCI-PCN	50 mg samples, methanol-water mixture (1:5 by vol)	$\lambda > 420$ nm	253.36	[62]
GTT-10%	10 mg samples, 40 mL aqueous solution containing 4 mL of TEOA	$\lambda > 420$ nm	925	This work

revealed the origins of states within the conduction band (CB), valence band (VB), and mid-gap states. It is found that the CB of PCN is primarily composed of both C p and N p orbitals, while the VB consisted mainly of N p orbital (Fig. S8a), suggesting the π -conjugated structure of PCN significantly influenced the band edges [63] (Fig. S8b). After doping, the Ga 4p orbitals contributed significantly near the conduction band (CB), indicating that Ga doping modulates the CB structure and facilitates electron transition. Notably, additional mid-gap states are observed at the Fermi level of Ga-K-PCN, which are composed of Ga 4p orbitals (Fig. 8a). The contribution of Ga atoms to the formation of these mid-gap states eventually led to the bandgap narrowing, aligning with the UV-Vis results. According to reported literature, the most stable relaxed configuration of K-CN is the interlayer bridging mode [45]. The s-orbital electrons of K were injected into the π -conjugated system of PCN, increasing the overall electron density.

Work function (Φ) refers to the minimum energy required for an electron to escape from the material's Fermi level to the vacuum level, reflecting the material's ability to bind electrons [64]. When two materials come into contact, electrons flow from the material with a lower work function (Ga-K-PCN, $\Phi=3.378$ eV) to the one with a higher work function (Ti₃C₂ MXene, $\Phi=4.118$ eV), until their Fermi levels align and thermal equilibrium is achieved (Fig. 8b-c). The electron transfer resulted in a positive charge on the Ga-K-PCN side at the interface due to the loss of electrons, while the Ti₃C₂ MXene side became negatively charged due to the gain of electrons, forming a built-in electric field pointing from Ti₃C₂ to Ga-K-PCN, which drives the migration of photo-generated electrons (e⁻) toward Ti₃C₂, thereby suppressing carrier recombination. In GTT-10%, the generated TiO_{2-x} intermediate layer may form a gradient band structure within the heterojunction system, further enhancing charge separation efficiency through a multi-stage electron transfer pathway (Fig. 8d), which is consistent with the data of TRPL.

Fig. 7. (a) Action spectra and (b) 3D stereoscopic image of PCN, Ga₁₀-K₃-PCN and GTT-A% under the light irradiation with the wavelength of 370 nm, 400 nm and 420 nm, (c) photocatalytic H₂ evolution for samples under full-spectrum and visible light, (d) effect of different scavengers for H₂ generation.

Fig. 8. (a) Density of states of Ga-K-PCN. Work function (Φ) of (b) Ga-K-PCN (111), (c) Ti_3C_2 MXene (001) and the optimized geometrical structure model (inset). (d) Schematic diagram of the interface interaction before and after contact. (e) Electron charge density distribution of Ga-K-PCN. Note: the yellow and blue areas represent electron accumulation and consumption, respectively, (f) planar-averaged electron density difference $\Delta\rho(z)$ for Ga-K-PCN/ Ti_3C_2 MXene.

Fig. 9. EPR spectra of GTT-10%: (a) $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{O}_2$, (b) $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{OH}$ and (c) $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{COO}\cdot\text{h}^+$ at 0 (dark), 5, 15, and 30 minutes of light irradiation. Comparison of the EPR signal intensity of used catalysts in this study after 30 minutes of light irradiation: (e) $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{O}_2$, (d) $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{OH}$ and (f) $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{COO}\cdot\text{h}^+$.

The charge density difference analysis was used to provide insights into the impact of metal doping on the redistribution and transfer of electrons in the carbon nitride. In pure PCN, the C atoms exhibited positive charge (δ^+), while the N atoms, especially the pyridine N in the triazine ring, accumulated negative charge (δ^-). The π -conjugated structure allows for charge delocalization within the plane, but interlayer charge transfer is limited (Fig. S8c). However, the distribution of electron charge density undergoes significant changes upon the introduction of doping elements. Ga^{3+} (electronegativity $\chi=1.81$) [65] caused the electrons of the surrounding N atoms (electronegativity $\chi=3.04$) [66] to shift toward Ga. As an electron-deficient center, Ga formed a localized positive charge region. Meanwhile, K^+ (low electronegativity $\chi=0.82$) inserted into the interlayer of PCN [67], weakening the interlayer van der Waals forces through electrostatic interactions and enhancing interlayer electron transfer. The charge polarization regions served as bifunctional catalytic active sites, synergistically promoting catalytic activity (Fig. 8e). For the GTT-10% heterojunction, electrons were redistributed at the interfacial area, extracted from Ga-K-PCN and then flowing into Ti_3C_2 (Fig. 8f), which is in good agreement with the Φ values.

3.7. Photocatalytic mechanism

The evolution of radical signals for catalysts under simulated sunlight irradiation was investigated using EPR spectroscopy. None of any signal was observed under dark conditions (0 min), confirming that the water-splitting H_2 production process is exclusively driven by light excitation (Fig. 9). In the GTT-10% system, the characteristic peaks of $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ adducts gradually intensified with increasing irradiation time (Fig. 9a). This phenomenon occurs because, upon photoexcitation, the loss of carbon atoms leads to the redistribution of excess electrons to the nearest N atoms and the delocalized π bonds, increasing the concentration of lone-pair electrons and consequently generating more $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$. Under the same illumination duration, the signal of $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ in the GTT-10% is stronger than that of the individual components (Fig. 9e), indicating that more electrons are able to migrate to the material surface to participate in the reduction of O_2 to generate $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ which may be attributed to the new catalytic active sites formed by the heterojunction (such as Ti-N coordination structures). It is noteworthy that the weak $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{OH}$ signal peak was solely observed in the GTT-10% heterojunction and was not detected in either the Ga-K-PCN or PCN systems (Fig. 9b&e). Additionally, the $\text{DMPO}\cdot\text{COO}^- \cdot \text{h}^+$ signal peak was not

observed in any of the three catalysts (Fig. 9c&f). This phenomenon is essentially the result of the combined effect of enhanced interfacial charge separation efficiency and optimized surface reaction kinetics. The GTT heterojunction interface promotes further charge carrier separation due to the built-in electric field at the interface. In contrast, pure PCN lacks an efficient electron acceptor, causing the holes to easily recombine with electrons and preventing the accumulation of sufficient concentration to generate $\cdot\text{OH}$. Furthermore, the surface functional groups of Ti_3C_2 MXene (such as $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{O}$) may directly participate in oxidation reactions, lowering the energy barrier for the oxidation of H_2O to $\cdot\text{OH}$, allowing h^+ to transiently exist and participate in the reactions. However, the rapid consumption of holes prevents their accumulation, making it impossible to reach a detectable concentration within EPR testing timeframe. A reasonable hypothesis is that the enriched Ti^{3+} in TiO_{2-x} may quench some of the h^+ and undergo secondary reactions with $\cdot\text{OH}$ ($\text{Ti}^{3+} + \cdot\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{Ti}^{4+} + \text{OH}^-$), further reducing the intensity of the $\cdot\text{OH}$ signal. The results of the EPR tests directly support the conclusions from the above radical capture experiments (Fig. S9), indicating that $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ are the primary reactive species and make the largest contribution to photocatalytic H_2 production.

In view of the analysis of the above results, a possible mechanism for photocatalytic water splitting to produce H_2 is proposed (Fig. 10). Upon visible-light excitation, e^- and h^+ were generated in the CB and VB of Ga-K-PCN, respectively (Eq. 6). Due to the natural formation of an internal electric field at the interface between Ti_3C_2 and Ga-K-PCN, the photoinduced e^- on the CB of Ga-K-PCN preferentially migrate to Ti_3C_2 through the ultrathin heterojunction nanosheets. Given that the CB position of Ga-K-PCN is more negative than the Fermi level of Ti_3C_2 , a Schottky barrier is established at the interface (Fig. 8d), significantly suppressing charge recombination from Ti_3C_2 back to Ga-K-PCN. During the photocatalysis process, e^- at the Fermi level of Ti_3C_2 react with O_2 to generate $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ (Eq. 7), and then $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ further reacts with H^+ in the solution to form $\cdot\text{OH}$. Since both the CB of Ga-K-PCN and the Fermi level of Ti_3C_2 are more negative than the hydrogen evolution potential (H^+/H_2 , 0 eV vs. NHE) (Fig. 8b&c), this contributes to the superior photocatalytic activities towards hydrogen evolution reaction. Meanwhile, the holes in Ga-K-PCN can be scavenged by the sacrificial agent TEOA.

Fig. 10. Pictorial representation of photocatalytic H_2 generation mechanism of GTT-10% heterojunction.

4. Conclusion

In summary, we have successfully constructed a defect-engineered Ga-K-PCN/Ti₃C₂ MXene@TiO_{2-x} ternary heterojunction through spontaneous MXene oxidation, which demonstrates significantly enhanced photocatalytic hydrogen evolution activity. The synergistic interplay between Ga-K doping, Ti₃C₂ MXene-derived TiO_{2-x} with partially oxidized titanium, and the hierarchical heterostructure architecture collectively contributes to the optimized light absorption, charge separation, and surface reaction dynamics. Specifically, the Ga-K co-doping tailors the electronic structure of PCN, extending visible-light absorption and introducing defect-mediated trapping centers to suppress carrier recombination. Meanwhile, the in-situ formed TiO_{2-x} layer bridges the interfacial charge transfer between Ga-K-PCN and MXene. The conductive MXene skeleton further accelerates electron transport and stabilizes the heterojunction interface. This work provides a novel strategy for designing multifunctional photocatalytic systems by integrating defect engineering with spontaneous interfacial oxidation, offering insights into the rational construction of MXene-based ternary heterostructure for sustainable energy conversion applications. Future research may focus on fine-tuning defect density and exploring the potential of extending this paradigm to other photocatalytic reactions, such as CO₂ reduction or nitrogen fixation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jingbo Ni: Writing – original draft, Data curation. **Yue Wang:** Formal analysis. **Lorenzo Sarasino:** Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maria Cristina Paganini:** Software, Resources. **Paola Calza:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Teruhisa Ohno:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Vittorio Boffa:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Jingbo Ni and Vittorio Boffa are inventors on Danish patent application no. PA 202530584 held by the Aalborg Universitet, titled ‘Photocatalyst for hydrogen production’.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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